

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL IMPACT DAMAGE EVALUATION OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Numerical simulation of static indentation and lateral impact tests of laminated composite plates, using a commercial finite element system is presented. Extensive results from a parametric study are also provided to supplement the experimental result. It is concluded that a nonlinear and transient response analysis was needed to predict the deformation and damage measured in the test.

1. INTRODUCTION

A sizable literature exists on numerical simulation of impact phenomenon [1] and on finite element analysis of transient and non-linear structural behaviour [2]. A comprehensive review of the literature on impact of laminated composite structures covering both numerical and experimental investigations was recently presented by Abrate [3]. An assessment of the very large number of references given in [3] reveals that studies that insist on validation of results either computed or measured are rather limited. Papers on impact response concentrate on computations with no attempt to correlate the numerical results with data recorded during tests. Equally large number of publications on impact testing provide only a qualitative/quantitative description of damage with no attempt to understand the dynamical behaviour of the target during the test through rigorous analyses. The objective of the present study, which is a natural extension of Ref. [4] is to bridge this gap.

Two representative experimental investigations [5,6] were identified for the present study. In each case, the test is fully specified including the contact force history so that finite element simulation can be performed. Measured responses including damage zones have been reported so that the success of the numerical simulation can be ascertained. Shivakuma et al. [5] have also presented a numerical analysis of static indentation tests of graphite/epoxy composite circular plates. However, the methods and procedures used are not general and the assumption of axi-symmetric deformation is questionable for other types of laminates and non-circular plates. Sciammarella and Subbaraman [6] have reported an experimental investigation of graphite/epoxy composite circular plates subjected to lateral impact. Spatial distribution of transverse displacement measured using holographic interferometry and damage zone measured using ultrasonic C-Scan are presented. However, no numerical simulation was attempted.

The present work deals with numerical simulation of static and impact tests of laminated composite plates described above, using a commercial FEM code. In the following sections a brief description of the methods and procedures used is given. numerical results from a parametric study are presented to supplement the experimental results.

2. METHODS AND PROCEDURES

A general purpose FEM code ABAQUS [7] was employed in the present study. This program has the capability to model multilayered anisotropic materials. It provides a library of finite elements suitable for static and dynamic analysis of plate and shell type structures taking into account membrane-bending coupling and transverse shear deformation effects. Among these, the S8R an isoparametric quadrilateral plate/shell element with 8 nodes and 6 engineering degrees of freedom per node is used in the present study. The user can specify within each element an arbitrary number of layers, each with its own thickness, ply-orientation and orthotropic elastic properties. The formulation uses a value of 5/6 for the shear correction factors as default. However, the user has the option to use any other value through independent input of transverse shear stiffness. The element output includes membrane, bending and transverse shear-stresses resultants either at the nodes or at the four integration points. The user can also request layer-stresses at the four integration points and at a maximum of three section points within each layer. However, the continuity of interlaminar normal and shear-stresses at the interface between plies is not satisfied a priori in the formulation.

ABAQUS provides four distinct procedures for linear/nonlinear analyses of structures subjected to static/dynamic loads. They are: (1) Linear static analysis (Procedure #1), (2) Non-linear Static analysis (procedure #2), (3) Linear transient response analysis (procedure #3) and (4) Non-linear transient responses analysis (procedure #4). In procedure #1, the maximum load is applied in a single step and a system of linear algebraic equation is solved using the Gaussian elimination method. In procedure #2, the load is applied incrementally and a system of non-linear algebraic equations is solved at each step using Newton's method or by user's choice using the quasi-Newton's method. An unconditionally stable, direct, implicit integration of the equation of motion is employed in procedures #3 and #4. However, the price of stability is the need to solve a system of linear/non-linear algebraic equations at each time step Δt . In principle, there is no mathematical limit on the size of Δt . In practice, Δt should be small enough to adequately define the contact force history. It is therefore essential to arrive at a fine enough mesh and small enough time step that can assure a converged solution.

The nature and extent of impact damage is estimated by first calculating the localised three-dimensional, time-dependent stress state around the point of impact and incorporating these in appropriate failure criteria. Multiple matrix cracks, fiber breaks and delaminations are the commonly observed failure modes. These failure modes with complex interaction between them complicate the prediction of onset and growth of impact damage. The tensor polynomial failure criteria proposed by Tsai and Wu [8] is employed in the present study to calculate the failure index (FI) given by:

$$FI = F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), F_i and F_{ij} are the strength tensors; σ_1 and σ_2 are the lamina stresses in the fiber direction and transverse direction respectively and σ_6 is the in-plane shear stress. Loci of points at which $FI = 1$ define the damage zone and the failure modes are identified using the maximum stress criteria [8].

An assessment of the methods and procedures described above for the prediction of impact response of composite plates was reported in [4]. Their application to the numerical simulation of static indentation and impact tests described in the introduction is presented in the next section.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Static Indentation Test of a Graphite/Epoxy Composite Circular Plate

The geometry, loading and boundary conditions used in the simulation are shown in Fig. 1. The ply-orientations/stacking sequences are $[0]_8$, $[0/90]_{2s}$, and $[45/0/-45/90]_1$. Finite element discrete of one quarter of the plate is also shown in the same figure. Test results for the quasi-isotropic laminate are reported in Ref. [5] and the cross-ply and unidirectional lay-ups are used in the parametric study. The material properties used in the computations are : $E_1 = 19.0 \times 10^6$ Psi (131.0 GPa) $E_2 = 1.89 \times 10^6$ Psi (13.0 GPa), $G_{12} = 0.93 \times 10^6$ Psi (6.4 GPa) and $\nu_{12} = 0.34$.

The calculated load versus load point displacement and spatial variation of the lateral displacement W are presented in Fig. 2 along with the test data taken from Ref. [5]. In general, the results predicted using procedure #2 are in good agreement with the experimental results. A comparison of the stress distribution across the laminate thickness calculated using procedures #1 and #2 shows that the difference is quite significant and hence consideration of geometric non-linearity in the numerical simulation is inevitable. The nature and extent of damage in the plate, estimated based on the results of non-linear analysis and at two different load levels, is shown in Fig. 3. It is to be noted that the damage zones located close to the clamped edge and at the center are in fact on the opposite surfaces of the plate. The damage zone around the load point agree very well with the test-data given in Ref. [5] in shape, size and orientation. However, the damage zone close to the clamped edge was not reported by Shivakumar et al. [5].

Variation in thickness and ply-orientation has a profound influence on the deformation and failure of the plate. For a thicker ($h = 0.08$ in.) and cross-ply laminated plate, computed results using procedure #2 are presented in Figs. 4 to 5. While the predicted load-deflection relation is linear (Fig. 4a), the spatial variation of the lateral displacement (Fig. 4b) features localised pinching effect. The nature and extent of damage is shown in Fig. 5 which also contains the damage in a quasi-isotropic laminate for comparison. The damage near the clamped edge predicted for a thin plate ($h = 0.04$) is absent in a thick plate ($h = 0.08$). The shape, size and orientation of the damage zone in a cross-ply laminated plate is shown to be drastically different from that in a quasi-isotropic laminate of same thickness.

The case of a unidirectional laminate is even more interesting. Figure 6 displays the predicted deformations. As shown in Fig. 6, the deformation is no longer axisymmetric and therefore the inadequacy of the numerical analysis procedure used by Shivakumar et al. [5] is evident.

3.3 Impact test of a Graphite/Epoxy composite circular plate

The test configuration employed by Sciamorella and Subbaraman [6] is shown in Fig. 7. The contact force history and finite element model used for the simulation is also given in the same figure. Material properties used in the computations are $E_1 = 20.16 \text{ E}6$ Psi, $E_2 = 1.4 \text{ E}6$ Psi, $G_{12} = 0.76 \text{ E}6$ Psi, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$ and $\rho = 1.45 \text{ E} - 4$ (lbs sec²/In⁴).

Results of static indentation tests conducted before and after impact testing of the plate are reported in Ref. [6]. The experimental technique used, namely, holographic interferometry had the necessary resolution to bring out the effect of impact induced damage on the subsequent deformations.

However, the measured change in bending rigidity associated with the damage was of the order of 4%. In Fig. 8a the measured displacement along a radial line is shown as test data, along with the calculated results obtained in the present study. Fig. 8b shows that the behaviour of the plate is highly non-linear. These results clearly demonstrate that procedure #2 has a key role in the numerical simulation of static indentation test of composite plates.

Fig. 9 provides a comparison of displacement - time histories at the point of impact calculated using procedures #3 and #4. The time step Δt used in the computations is $\Delta t = T/29$, where T is the period of fundamental mode of undamped free vibrations of the target. The calculated value of T being 0.7204 milliseconds. Equilibrium iteration is stopped within each step when specified tolerances on membrane and bending stress resultants are satisfied. The predicted response in both cases is oscillatory and the difference is mainly due to the large deflections. The effect of non-linear stiffening is not only to damp the amplitude but also to shorten the period of oscillations.

A comparison of the deformed shape of the plate as a function of time after impact, predicted using linear and non-linear analyses is made in Fig. 10. The results based on procedure #4 are closer to the measurements made on damage plates shown in Ref. [6].

The duration t_c for which the contact force acts, in comparison with T , is also a parameter influencing the response. The results presented in Fig. 9 correspond to $(t_c / T) = 0.35$. Similar results for $(t_c / T) = 1.0$ are presented in Fig. 11. Focusing first on procedure #3, the predicted response is still oscillatory and the peak amplitude is much larger than in Fig. 9. Since the maximum load is the same in both cases, this phenomenon is attributed to the difference in momenta. Now focusing on procedure #4 in Fig. 11, the effect of non-linear stiffening is seen to damp the amplitude very significantly. However, the period of oscillation does not change much.

A comparison of estimated and measured damage zones is made in Fig. 12. It is emphasized that the identified failure mode within the measured damage zone in Ref. [6] was delaminations. However, the failure mode predicted in the present study was matrix cracking. The notable difference between measured and calculated damage zones in Fig. 12 is therefore explained

4. CLOSURE

Numerical simulation of static indentation and lateral impact tests of laminated composite plates, using a commercial finite element system is presented. Based on the results obtained, it is fair to draw the following conclusions. 1) The material models, finite elements and analysis procedures implemented in ABAQUS (version 4-7) are able to provide numerical results that correlate well with measured data. 2) Nonlinear and transient response analysis using direct implicit integration of the equation of motion is indispensable for reliable prediction of impact response. 3) Through parametric studies, it is also possible to study in a systematic manner complicating effects such as plate shape, thickness, ply-orientations and duration of impact on deformation and failure. 4) Impact testing alone can not provide a complete solution to the problem of impact response, mainly due to limitations of available test-facilities instrumentation and data acquisition systems. Combined use of finite element simulation and impact-testing is therefore necessary for assessing damage tolerance of composite structures.

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Fig. 1. Finite element simulation of static indentation tests on G/epoxy circular plates.

Fig. 2. Deformation of a G/epoxy plate. numerical results versus test data.

Fig. 3. Nature and extent of damage in a G/epoxy circular plate.

Fig. 5. Comparison of damage zones in G/epoxy circular plates.

Fig. 4. Deformation of a cross-ply laminated G/epoxy circular plate.

Fig. 6. Deformation of a G/epoxy circular plate: unidirectional laminate.

Fig. 7. Finite element simulation of impact test on a G/epoxy circular plate.

Fig. 8. Comparison of calculated displacements with test data, (case in Fig. 7).

Fig. 9. Comparison of linear and nonlinear solutions, (case in Fig. 7).

Fig. 10. Displacements predicted using Proc.#3 and Proc.#4. (case in Fig.7).

Fig. 11. Comparison of linear and nonlinear solutions. (case in Fig.7)

Fig. 12. Comparison of predicted and measured damage zone. (case in Fig. 7)

Fig. 13. Growth of impact induced damage (case in Fig. 7).